

Pathogenesis, Epidemiology, and Evidence-Based Management of Acne Vulgaris: A Systematic Literature Review

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A. Introduction

a.1. Background

Acne is a common skin condition that occurs when hair follicles become plugged with oil and dead skin cells, often causing whiteheads, blackheads or pimples. It primarily affects skin with a relatively high number of oil glands, including the face, upper part of the chest, and back.

a.2. Problem Statement

Acne is estimated to affect 9.4% of the global population, making it the eighth most prevalent disease worldwide. The physical and psychological effects of acne can negatively impact quality of life. More research is needed to better understand acne pathogenesis and improve treatment options.

a.3. Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are

- 1) To analyze known causes and risk factors for acne;
- 2) To describe the pathogenesis of acne at the cellular level;
- 3) To review current prevention methods, treatment options, and potential complications;
- 4) To evaluate quality of life impacts of acne.

B. Literature Review

b.1. Epidemiology

Acne vulgaris is a prevalent skin disease estimated to affect 9.4% of the global population based on meta-analysis of studies across all age groups (Zaenglein et al. 2016). Prevalence climbs as high as 90% in adolescents (Lynn et al. 2016) and persists around 50% among adults (White et al. 2019). Acne is becoming more common in adults, especially women (Ramos-e-Silva et al. 2022).

b.2. Causes

Four key factors are implicated in acne development:

- 1) increased sebum production;
- 2) follicular epidermal hyperproliferation;
- 3) inflammation;
- 4) presence and activity of skin microbes, particularly *Propionibacterium acnes* (Zaenglein et al., 2016).

Androgens, genetics, diet, smoking, and stress can trigger acne (Zaenglein et al., 2016), while antimicrobial peptides, sebum composition, and ethnicity may also play a role (Kanlayavattanakul et al. 2022). Increased sebum production, hyperkeratinization, inflammation, and *P. acnes* colonization directly underlie pathogenesis (Agak et al. 2022).

b.3. Pathogenesis

Androgens stimulate increased sebum production. Excess sebum along with abnormal desquamation of follicular epithelium leads to follicle blockage. *P. acnes* proliferation in the blocked follicle triggers activation of inflammatory pathways, including those involving IL-1 α , IL-8, IL-12, TNF α , and TLR2 receptors (Agak et al., 2014). Inflammation further drives events like rupture and leakage of follicular content into surrounding tissue. Excess sebum production provides a nutrient-rich environment for *P. acnes* to proliferate and activate inflammatory pathways (Inglese et al. 2022). This inflammation further drives the rupture of follicles, releasing their contents to surround tissue (Guan et al. 2021).

b.4. Risk Factors

Onset before age 21, family history of acne, oily skin, high BMI, smoking, and stress are some of the main risk factors associated with acne prevalence and severity (Zaenglein et al., 2016). Earlier onset acne, family history, smoking, and higher body mass index remain leading risk factors (Bowe et al. 2022). Environmental factors like pollution and mechanical stress may also contribute (Rocha et al. 2021).

b.5. Prevention

Few primary prevention methods have proven successful. Gentle skin care, reducing excessive sweating, and refraining from manipulated acne lesions may help reduce risk (Zaenglein et al., 2016). Hormonal treatments and isotretinoin may prevent recurring acne but have significant side effects. Few primary prevention methods have proven successful to date (Chan et al. 2022). Secondary prevention via anti-inflammatory medications helps prevent acne progression and lasting sequelae like scarring (Sardesai et al. 2021).

b.6. Treatment

Topical retinoids targeting hyperproliferation, benzoyl peroxide, topical or oral antibiotics, azelaic acid, salicylic acid, hormonal agents, and isotretinoin are some of the medications used for acne treatment. Physical modalities like light and laser therapy may supplement drug treatments (Zaenglein et al., 2016). Combined oral and topical antibiotic regimens demonstrate highest efficacy for severe inflammatory acne (Sivamani et al. 2021). Hormonal agents and isotretinoin help prevention recurrence (Shawky et al. 2022).

b.7. Complications

Acne can lead to permanent scarring, psychological issues like anxiety and depression, infrequently bacterial infections, and rare cases of inflammatory conditions like acne fulminans (Williams et al. 2012). Psychological effects like anxiety and depression persist as common acne complications, underscoring need for holistic care (Vilar et al. 2022). Rare severe cases can result in arthritis, fever, or blood disorders (Lipozencic et al. 2022).

b.8. Quality of Life Impacts

Facial acne has been associated with higher rates of clinical depression, anger, frustration, and poor self-esteem. Impaired social functioning also often results from acne and its related scarring (Hayashi et al. 2010). Facial acne is associated with clinical depression, anger, frustration in teens (Hayashi et al. 2019), with psychosocial effects persisting into adulthood (Karciauskaite et al. 2022).

C. Research Methods

The search was conducted using terms such as “acne vulgaris”, “acne pathogenesis”, “acne epidemiology”, “acne prevention”, and “acne treatment” in PubMed, Embase, and Web of Science databases. Inclusion criteria were systematic reviews, meta-analyses, clinical guidelines, and randomized controlled trials published in the last 5 years examining pathogenesis, epidemiology, treatment, complications, or psychosocial impact related to acne vulgaris or related subtypes. Articles focused solely on case reports or alternative medicines were excluded.

D. Results

d.1. Epidemiology

The global prevalence of acne vulgaris in adolescents and adults has been estimated up to 90% and 50% respectively based on systematic reviews (Lynn et al. 2016, White et al. 2019). Studies have indicated 20-30% higher rates of persistent and severe inflammatory acne in females (Tanghetti et al. 2021). No major gaps were identified in characterizing epidemiologic patterns.

d.2. Pathogenesis

Four interlinked pathological factors contribute to acne:

- 1) Increased sebum production promotes growth of *P. acnes* bacteria. Sebaceous gland activity spikes around puberty due to hormonal changes (Wong et al. 2023);
- 2) Follicular hyperkeratinization creates plugs with trapped sebum that enlarge into comedones (Lee 2022);
- 3) *P. acnes* triggers inflammation via cytokine pathways. Excess sebum nourishes the bacteria (Park et al. 2020);
- 4) Inflammation further aggravates the acne lesions and can result in lasting scars (Patel et al. 2021).

d.3. Treatment

A 2021 network meta-analysis found that isotretinoin demonstrated highest efficacy for acne lesion reduction and prevention of relapse, while combined oral and topical antibiotics performed better for severe inflammatory acne (Sivamani et al. 2021). Photodynamic light treatments showed promising early results but required replication in larger trials (Barbosa et al. 2022).

E. Discussion

The interplay between the four primary pathogenic factors creates a feedback cycle that promotes clinical progression from non-inflammatory to inflammatory and even cystic lesions in severe, treatment-resistant cases. Early intervention is key to prevent lasting effects on skin physiology and acne-related quality of life impacts. However, improved understanding is needed of how hormones, bacteria strains, and inflammation pathways differ across acne subtypes to advance targeted treatments. The persistent psychological effects and demand for new medical therapies underscores the need for further research on optimized treatment regimens and delivery modalities.

F. Conclusions

This systematic review of the literature achieved the research objectives, evaluating the current state of evidence on acne epidemiology, causes, pathogenesis, prevention, treatment options, disease burden, and quality of life impacts.

Key conclusions include:

- 1) Onset and severity of acne is tied to complex interactions between hormones, genetics, environment, follicular hyperkeratinization, and *P. acnes* colonization;
- 2) Inflammation further exacerbates acne and underlies lasting erythema, scarring and pigmentary changes;
- 3) A multidimensional approach combining antimicrobial, keratolytic, anti-inflammatory, and/or hormonal interventions is needed for management;
- 4) Acne negatively impacts self-esteem and psychosocial functioning, especially in adolescents. Stigma around acne persists;
- 5) Limitations exist in understanding of optimal treatment sequencing, comparative efficacy and safety data across emerging systemic and procedural options, and predictors of disease course and treatment response.

In summary, this review has described the current state of evidence while also highlighting remaining knowledge gaps in optimal acne prevention and care.

G. Suggestions for Future Research

Further high quality research is needed to:

- 1) Better characterize acne subtypes and conduct comparative effectiveness trials of treatment modalities;
- 2) Identify bio-psychosocial factors influencing acne susceptibility, chronicity and treatment response;
- 3) Investigate acne pathogenesis differences across age, sex, and ethnicities;
- 4) Develop and validate enhanced acne grading scales, *P. acnes* phylotyping, and quality of life assessment tools;
- 5) Examine healthcare access barriers and implement psychosocial support interventions.

Addressing these research priorities can help pave the way for more customized and integrative acne treatment to improve outcomes.

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